

Chr2:heterozygosity for 5 bins based on PC1 in PCAngsd



Chr2:134700000-135900000



Chr5:heterozygosity for 5 bins based on PC1 in PCAngsd



Chr5:55400000-55500000



Chr6:heterozygosity for 5 bins based on PC1 in PCAngsd



Chr6:40000-100000



Chr7:heterozygosity for 5 bins based on PC1 in PCAngsd



Chr7:56200000-56300000



Chr13:heterozygosity for 5 bins based on PC1 in PCAngsd



Chr14:heterozygosity for 5 bins based on PC1 in PCAngsd



Chr16.1:heterozygosity for 5 bins based on PC1 in PCAngsd



Chr16.2:heterozygosity for 5 bins based on PC1 in PCAngsd



Chr16.3:heterozygosity for 5 bins based on PC1 in PCAngsd



Chr17:heterozygosity for 5 bins based on PC1 in PCAngsd



Chr18:heterozygosity for 5 bins based on PC1 in PCAngsd



Chr22:heterozygosity for 5 bins based on PC1 in PCAngsd



Chr25.1:heterozygosity for 5 bins based on PC1 in PCAngsd



Chr25.2:heterozygosity for 5 bins based on PC1 in PCAngsd

